

Supporting Information

Thermoelectric Properties of 2,7-Dipyridylfluorene Derivatives in Single-Molecule Junctions

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1. Theoretical calculations

a. Geometry of isolated molecules and their junctions

The DFT code (SIESTA) was used to obtain fully relaxed geometries of the isolated fluorene molecules, as shown in Figure S1.

Figure S1. Fully relaxed isolated fluorene molecules: **1** Fl-H, **2** Fl-Me, **3** Fl-OMe, **4** Fl-CF₃ and **5** Fl-O (top to bottom).

The series of molecules were then connected to gold electrodes and the geometries were relaxed. The structures are shown in Figure S2.

Figure S2. Fluorene derivatives in Au|molecule|Au junctions: **1** Fl-H, **2** Fl-Me, **3** Fl-OMe, **4** Fl-CF₃ and **5** Fl-O (top to bottom).

b. Binding energy of 4 FI-CF₃ on gold

To calculate the optimum binding distance for the fluorene series between two gold(111) surfaces, DFT and the counterpoise method were used, which removes basis set superposition errors (BSSE). The binding distance z was defined as the distance between the gold surface and the N atom of the molecule. The ground state energy of the total system was calculated using SIESTA and is denoted E_{AB}^{AB} , with the parameters defined in the experimental section of the main text. Here the gold leads consist of 6 layers of 30 atoms. The energy of each monomer was then calculated in a fixed basis, which is achieved through the use of ghost atoms in SIESTA. Hence the energy of the individual molecule in the presence of the fixed basis is defined as E_A^{AB} and for the isolated gold as E_B^{AB} . The binding energy is then calculated using the following equation S1:

$$\text{Binding Energy} = E_{AB}^{AB} - E_A^{AB} - E_B^{AB} \quad (\text{S1})$$

As an example, Figure S3 shows the binding energy calculation for molecule **4**. Almost identical binding energies were obtained for the other four molecules **1-3** and **5**.

Figure S3. Left panel: Binding energy of **4** attached to gold as a function of molecule-contact distance. The equilibrium distance (i.e. the minimum of the binding energy curve) is approximately 2.4 Å for **4**. Right panel: molecule **4** attached to a gold lead.

c. Wave function plots.

The plots below show the isosurfaces of the HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 of the isolated molecules **1-5**.

$E_F = -3.53$ eV

HOMO $E = -5.25$ eV

LUMO $E = -2.31$ eV

HOMO-1 $E = -5.25$ eV

LUMO+1 $E = -1.56$ eV

Figure S4. Wave function for molecule 1 (Fl-H). Top panel: Fully optimized geometry. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

Figure S5. Wave function for molecule 2 (Fl-Me). Top panel: Fully optimized geometry. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

$E_F = -3.97$ eV

HOMO $E = -5.23$ eV

LUMO $E = -2.50$ eV

HOMO-1 $E = -5.23$ eV

LUMO+1 $E = -1.79$ eV

Figure S6. Wave function for molecule 3 (FI-OMe). Top panel: Fully optimized geometry. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

$E_F = -4.52$ eV

HOMO $E = -5.24$ eV

LUMO $E = -2.50$ eV

HOMO-1 $E = -5.24$ eV

LUMO+1 $E = -1.66$ eV

Figure S7. Wave function for molecule 4 (FI-CF₃). Top panel: Fully optimized geometry. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

$E_F = -4.55$ eV

HOMO $E = -5.28$ eV

LUMO $E = -3.13$ eV

HOMO-1 $E = -5.29$ eV

LUMO+1 $E = -2.38$ eV

Figure S8. Wave function for molecule **5** (Fl-O). Top panel: Fully optimized geometry. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

Figures S4-S7 show that there is no frontier orbital distribution on the pendant group for molecules **1-4**, whereas Figure S8 shows a contribution of the HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1 on the oxygen atom of fluorenone derivative **5**. This distribution clearly appears in the transmission curve of **5** as a resonance in Figure S9. This feature will be discussed in more detail later in the theoretical model (Section 1f). The HOMOs of these molecules are degenerate as shown in the left panels of Figures S4-S8.

d. HOMO-LUMO gaps

The calculated and optically measured HOMO-LUMO gaps are listed in Table S1. Theoretical gaps were calculated for isolated molecules and when the molecules are in the junctions, the gap between their HOMO and LUMO transmission resonances is quoted. As shown by the third and fourth columns in Table S1, isolated gaps are larger than the gaps between the transmission resonances. This is because the latter are shifted by the real part of the self-energy of the contact to the leads, reflecting the fact that the system is more open when contacted to electrodes. To obtain a more accurate HOMO-LUMO gap, we use a scissor correction as described in the main text.

Table S1: Experimental measurements and theoretical calculations of HOMO–LUMO gaps in eV.

Molecule	^a E_g (Exp.)	^b $E_{g, \text{DFT}}$ (Iso.)	^c $E_{g, \text{DFT}}$ (Au M Au)
1 FI-H	3.80	2.85	2.56
2 FI-Me	3.78	2.83	2.54
3 FI-OMe	3.84	2.69	2.54
4 FI-CF₃	3.95	2.69	2.61
5 FI-O	3.84	2.51	2.42

^a Experimental data: $E_g = 1240/\lambda_{\text{onset Abs.}}$ ^b Theoretical HOMO–LUMO gaps for the isolated molecules.

^c Theoretical gaps between HOMO–LUMO transmission resonances in Au|molecule|Au structures.

e. Transmission coefficients

The transmission coefficient $T(E)$ was calculated for the fluorene molecules **1-5**. Figure S9 suggests that the conductance values of **1-4** are approximately the same when the Fermi energy lies in the tail of the LUMO. The $T(E)$ of **5** has a resonance close to $E = -2.0$ eV. This is consistent with the HOMO wave function plot in Figure S8, which shows a significant weight on the oxygen atom.

Figure S9. Transmission coefficients $T(E)$ for molecules **1-5** (without scissor correction).

f. Theoretical model for **5 FI-O**

Although the resonance at $E = -2$ eV is far from the expected experimental Fermi energy and therefore does not affect the electrical conductance, it is of interest theoretically to explore its origin. The HOMO plot for molecule **5** in Figure S8 shows a significant weight on the oxygen atom. To prove that this bound state is the origin of the transmission resonance near $E = -2$ eV, the following plots show the effect on the transmission coefficient of moving a water molecule dipole gradually away from the pendant oxygen atom (see top panel of Fig S10).

Figure S10. Zero bias transmission coefficient $T(E)$ of a gating model (**5** FI-O), curves labelled d when a water molecule is present at two distances 2.0 and 2.8 Å.

Figure S10 lower panel shows the effect of this electrostatic gating process. During successive gating steps the transmission resonances move from higher energy to lower energy when **5** is in the vicinity of a water molecule. The molecules **2-4** with pendant Me, OMe and CF_3 groups also have resonances due to the pendant groups.¹ However, these resonances are outside the HOMO-LUMO gap and therefore are not relevant experimentally.

g. Seebeck coefficient

Figure S11 shows that the five molecules possess a similar Seebeck coefficient, in agreement with the experimental measurements.

Figure S11. Calculated Seebeck coefficient S of **1-5** using scissor corrections.

2. Molecular synthesis

a. General details

376 or 400 MHz NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance-400 MHz instruments. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm and referenced to TMS or residual solvent. ^{13}C NMR

(151 or 176 MHz) spectral data were collected on Varian VNMRS-700 MHz spectrometers. All melting points were measured using a Stuart SMP40 melting point apparatus. The temperatures at the melting point were ramped at 1 °C/min and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis was performed at the Elemental Microanalysis Service of Durham University (UK) using an Exeter CE-400 Elemental Analyzer. MALDI TOF MS Mass spectrometry and high resolution mass spectra were obtained using a Autoflex II ToF/ToF (Bruker) and a LCT Premier XE (Waters) respectively. All chemicals were purchased from Acros Organics, Sigma Aldrich or Alfa Aesar and used without further treatment. Dry solvents were obtained from a solvent purification system. All air-sensitive reactions were conducted under a blanket of argon which was dried by passage through a column of phosphorus pentoxide. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel from Sigma Aldrich. UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded at room-temperature using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer Evolution 220 from Thermo Scientific. Photoluminescence spectra were recorded on a Horiba Jobin Yvon SPEX Fluorolog 3-22 spectrofluorometer in quartz cuvettes with a path length of 10 mm.

b. Synthetic procedures

α,α -bis(trifluoromethyl)-1,1'-biphenyl-2-methanol **B**

A solution of 2-biphenylcarbonyl chloride **A**² (4.23 g, 19.5 mmol) in dry 1,2-dimethoxyethane (50 mL) was cooled to -60 °C. Then, Me₃SiCF₃ (5.77 mL, 39.0 mmol) and [Me₄N]F (3.63 g, 39.0 mmol) were added and the solution was stirred at -30 °C for 1 h. The reaction was then allowed to warm at room temperature and was stirred for 18 h under argon. An aqueous solution of HCl (50 mL, 2 M) was added, the organic layer was extracted with ether, washed with water (20 mL), dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent was evaporated. The addition of hexane to the mixture led to the formation of a white precipitate which was filtered off. The filtrate was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using hexane with a gradient of EtOAc (0 – 15%) as eluent. The product **B** was isolated as colorless crystals (1.78 g, 30%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.77 (1H, m), 7.46 (5H, m), 7.37 (1H,

m), 3.45 (1H, s). ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3): δ -74.98 (6F, s). These data are in agreement with the literature data for **B** synthesized by a different route.³

2,7-diiodo-9,9-di(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **D**

B was converted into **C** (82% yield) and **C** was converted into **D** as described in the literature.³ **D** (470 mg, 62%) was characterized as follows: ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.07 (2H, s), 7.91 (2H, dd, $J = 8.1, 1.5$ Hz), 7.50 (2H, d, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 3.45 (1H, s). ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3): δ -68.23 (6F, s). These data are in agreement with the literature.³

2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene

Concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.24 mL, 4.44 mmol) and dry trimethylorthoformate (4.88 mL, 46.80 mmol) were added to a suspension of 2,7-dibromo-9-fluorenone (1.0 g, 2.96 mmol) in dry methanol (200 mL). The reaction was stirred for 48 h at reflux and then cooled to room temperature prior to the addition of Et_3N (until pH 7 was achieved). The white precipitate was filtered off and washed with MeOH. Then the filtrate was concentrated under high vacuum; the precipitate was again filtered and washed as above. Recrystallization in hexane gave white crystals of 2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene (1.14 g, 98%). mp: 180.0 °C. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.66 (2H, dd, $J = 1.8, 0.6$ Hz), 7.54 (2H, dd, $J = 8.1, 1.8$ Hz), 7.44 (2H, dd, $J = 8.01, 0.6$ Hz), 3.36 (6H, s). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 143.76, 138.19, 133.56, 128.34, 122.51, 121.91, 107.36, 52.10. Anal Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_2$: C 46.91, H 3.15; found C 47.19, H 3.23.

2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethylfluorene **2**

2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethylfluorene (500 mg, 1.43 mmol), 4-pyridyl boronic acid (440 mg, 3.57 mmol), Na_2CO_3 (606 mg, 5.72 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (545 mg, 0.47 mmol) were dissolved in a degassed mixture of 1,2-dimethoxyethane/distilled water (40 mL/20 mL). After 24 h of stirring at reflux under argon, the reaction was cooled to room temperature, extracted with DCM and dried over MgSO_4 . Purification performed through silica gel using DCM with a gradient of EtOAc (from 0 to 90%) followed by recrystallization in MeOH gave white crystals of **2** (330 mg, 66%). mp: 224.1 °C. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.68 (4H, dd, $J = 4.4, 1.7$ Hz), 7.83 (2H, dd, $J = 7.9, 0.6$ Hz), 7.71 (2H, d, $J = 1.2$ Hz), 7.63 (2H, dd, $J = 7.9, 1.7$ Hz), 7.57 (4H, dd, $J = 4.4, 1.7$ Hz), 1.59 (6H, s). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 155.17, 150.56, 148.69, 139.66, 137.94, 126.61, 121.88, 121.56, 121.24, 47.51, 27.45. HRMS-ASAP⁺, calcd for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2$: 348.1626; found (m/z): 348.1615. Anal Calcd for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2$: C 86.17, H 5.79, N 8.04; found C 85.77, H 5.84, N 7.94.

2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene **3**

2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene (110 mg, 0.29 mmol), 4-pyridyl boronic acid (89 mg, 0.72 mmol), Na_2CO_3 (122 mg, 1.15 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (115 mg, 0.10 mmol) were dissolved in a degassed mixture of 1,2-dimethoxyethane/distilled water (10 mL/5 mL). After 24 h of stirring at reflux under argon, the reaction was cooled to room temperature, extracted with DCM, dried over MgSO_4 and solvents were evaporated under high vacuum. Purification was performed on silica using as eluent a gradient of EtOAc in DCM (from 0 to 80%) followed by DCM with 3% of MeOH. Then recrystallization in acetonitrile gave a yellow

powder of **3** (60 mg, 55%). mp: 213.1 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.70 (4H, dd, *J* = 4.5, 1.7 Hz), 7.85 (2H, d, *J* = 1.0 Hz), 7.78 (2H, dd, *J* = 7.9, 0.7 Hz), 7.74 (2H, dd, *J* = 7.9, 1.7 Hz), 7.58 (4H, dd, *J* = 4.5, 1.7 Hz), 3.44 (6H, s). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 150.77, 148.08, 143.45, 140.43, 138.68, 129.53, 123.57, 121.84, 121.52, 107.83, 52.23.

2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-bis(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **4**

2,7-diiodo-9,9-bis(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **D** (200 mg, 0.36 mmol), 4-pyridyl boronic acid (111 mg, 0.90 mmol), Na₂CO₃ (153 mg, 1.44 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (138 mg, 0.12 mmol) were dissolved in a degassed mixture of 1,2-dimethoxyethane/distilled water (12 mL/6 mL). After 24 h of stirring at reflux under argon, the reaction was cooled to room temperature, extracted with DCM and dried over MgSO₄. Purification on silica gel using hexane then a gradient of MeOH in EtOAc (from 0 to 5%) followed by a recrystallization in hexane led to the isolation of white crystals of **4** (110 mg, 67%). mp: 187.4 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.73 (4H, dd, *J* = 4.4, 1.7 Hz), 8.04 (2H, s), 8.94 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz), 7.87 (2H, dd, *J* = 7.9, 1.7 Hz), 7.57 (4H, dd, *J* = 4.4, 1.7 Hz). ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃): δ -68.15 (6F, s). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 150.80, 147.53, 142.70, 139.38, 136.31, 130.42, 125.37, 121.99, 121.96. HRMS-ES⁺, calcd for C₂₅H₁₄F₆N₂: 456.1061; found (m/z) [M+H]⁺: 457.1146.

d) Copies of NMR spectra

Figure S12. ¹H NMR spectrum of α,α -bis(trifluoromethyl)-1,1'-biphenyl-2-methanol **B**

Figure S13. ¹⁹F NMR spectrum of α,α -bis(trifluoromethyl)-1,1'-biphenyl-2-methanol **B**

Figure S14. ^1H NMR spectrum of 2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene

Figure S15. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 2,7-dibromo-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene

Figure S16. ^1H NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethylfluorene **2**

Figure S17. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethylfluorene **2**

Figure S17. ¹H NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene **3**

Figure S18. ¹³C NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-dimethoxyfluorene **3**

Figure S20. ¹H NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-bis(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **4**

Figure S21. ¹⁹F NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-bis(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **4**

Figure S22. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 2,7-dipyridinyl-9,9-bis(trifluoromethyl)fluorene **4**

e. Absorption and fluorescence spectra. The absorption and emission spectra of compounds **1-5** were recorded in dichloromethane solution at room temperature. The spectra are shown in Figure S23 and their wavelengths are summarized in Table S2. The spectra are characteristic of fluorene⁴ and fluorenone⁵ derivatives, with absorption in the ultraviolet region and emission in the blue region.

Figure S23. Normalized absorption (solid lines) and fluorescence (dashed lines) spectra.

Table S2. Absorption and fluorescence wavelengths recorded at room temperature in DCM.

Compound	FI-H 1	FI-Me 2	FI-OMe 3	FI-CF ₃ 4	FI-O 5
λ_{\max} abs (nm)	326	328	325	314	286, 323, 334
λ_{\max} PL (nm)	358, 375, 400	361, 379, 402	361, 379, 403	351, 367, 387, 414	Non-emissive

3. Conductance and thermopower measurements

a. Sample preparation

After annealing, the STM images of the gold substrate typically show clean surfaces with crystalline reconstruction of the gold surface and monoatomic steps (as shown in Figure S24), while G- Δz curves between the Au-Au electrodes show tunneling behavior in ambient conditions (see also ref. 10 in the manuscript).

Figure S24. STM images of the Au substrate in ambient conditions.

b) Experimental techniques

Scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) measurements were performed using a home-built STM modified to measure simultaneously the conductance G and thermopower S of single-molecule junctions.⁶ Mechanically cut Au tips (0.25 mm diameter, 99.99% purity, Goodfellow) were used to contact the molecules. STM-BJ measurements⁶ were performed in ambient conditions and at room temperature, with a bias voltage V_{bias} of 200 mV applied to the substrate. Single-molecule junctions were formed after breaking the Au-Au contact formed by indenting the substrate with the STM tip. A 12 M Ω resistor in series with the tip-sample junction was used in order to monitor the Au-Au one-atom contact. Amplification of the current was performed using a double-stage, home-made, linear current-voltage (I-V)-converter with an overall gain of $2.6 \cdot 10^{10}$ V/A.

A 1 k Ω resistor mounted in the tip support was used as a heater to establish a temperature difference ΔT between the substrate (at room temperature, T_c) and the tip (heated at a temperature $T_h > T_c$). Thermoelectric properties of each molecule were measured by applying four different ΔT s, namely $\Delta T = T_h - T_c = 0$ K, ~ 15 K, ~ 22 K and ~ 30 K, monitored with thermocouples in the resistor and substrate. For each ΔT , the system was allowed to stabilize for approximately 20 min before measurements were taken.

A thermovoltage V_{th} is generated in the junction as a consequence of the temperature difference applied. V_{th} consists of a contribution from the molecular junction $S\Delta T$ and a contribution from the tip-connecting lead $S_{lead}(-\Delta T)$, where S_{lead} is the thermopower of the lead. The current between the tip and substrate is given by

$$I = G(V_{bias} - V_{th}) = G(V_{bias} + S_{lead}\Delta T - S\Delta T) \quad (S2)$$

where G is the conductance of the junction (Figure S25). Taking into account that for $V_{bias} = V_{th}$ the current vanishes, by measuring a current-voltage (I - V) curve the thermopower and

the conductance can be simultaneously obtained: the zero crossing yields V_{th} (and hence S) and the slope gives G .

Figure S25. Experimental technique for the simultaneous measurement of conductance and thermopower. a,b) Tip displacement Δz and applied bias voltage ΔV at the molecular junction, respectively, as a function of time. The bias voltage is maintained at a fixed value V_{bias} during the tip motion (in blue in a) and every few picometers it is swept twice between $\pm\Delta V_0$ while the tip is stationary (in red in a). In the experiments, the bias voltage V_{bias} was set to 200 mV, ΔV_0 was set to 10 mV and the tip was stopped every 40-60 pm. c) Experimental I - V curves showing the voltage offset due to the temperature difference.

The thermopower S of single-molecule junctions was measured during the breaking of the junction, stopping the tip motion every 40-60 pm, as depicted in Figure S25. The bias voltage was maintained at a fixed value $\Delta V = V_{bias} = 200$ mV during the tip motion and it was swept twice every few picometers between $\pm\Delta V_0 = \pm 10$ mV while the tip is stationary. I - V curves show a voltage offset when measuring in the presence of a temperature difference ΔT between the two Au electrodes. This voltage offset corresponds to the thermovoltage V_{th} of the junction (once the electrical offsets are taken into account). Experiments were performed at zero ΔT and at three different ΔT values for each molecule to ensure a good linear fit of all the V_{th} values. By fitting the peak of the thermovoltage histograms of V_{th} at each ΔT to Gaussian distributions, from the mean value of the fit the most probable values $\overline{V_{th}}$ of the

single-molecule junctions are determined at each temperature and its standard deviation $\sigma_{V_{th}}$. The conductance is measured both from the current values while moving the tip ($V_{bias} = 200$ mV) and from the slope of the I - V curves.

c) Conductance G and thermopower S vs. tip displacement Δz

After breaking the Au-Au contact, a molecular junction connecting a single molecule between both electrodes may be formed (which shows a plateau in the G - Δz curve) (see Figure S26) or, indeed, the tip may retract without connecting any molecule and hence, no plateau is observed. Table S3 gives the value of the ratio of the curves with plateau to overall acquired curves for each molecule.

Table S3. Percentage of G - Δz curves showing a plateau.

Molecule	Ratio
1 FI-H	48%
2 FI-Me	54%
3 FI-OMe	77%
4 FI-CF₃	71%
5 FI-O	55%

Figure S26. Conductance G vs. tip displacement Δz 2D histograms. The zero displacement was chosen to be the position where $G = 0.1 G_0$.

The thermovoltage measured on the conductance plateau does not show any dependence on tip displacement as can be seen in Figures S27 and S28, corresponding to molecule **3** at a temperature difference of $\Delta T = 0$ K and 22 K, respectively.

Figure S27. 2D histograms for molecule **3** when $\Delta T = 0$ K. a) Conductance G vs. tip displacement Δz 2D histogram. The zero displacement was chosen to be the position where $G = 0.1 G_0$. b) Thermovoltage V_{th} vs. tip displacement Δz 2D histogram. c) Conductance G vs. thermovoltage V_{th} 2D histogram.

Figure S28. 2D histograms for molecule **3** when $\Delta T \sim 22$ K. a) Conductance G vs. tip displacement Δz 2D histogram. The zero displacement was chosen to be the position where $G = 0.1 G_0$. b) Thermovoltage V_{th} vs. tip displacement Δz 2D histogram. c) Conductance G vs. thermovoltage V_{th} 2D histogram.

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